

Which Rare Diseases Are Best Suited to Diagnostic AI? Towards a Systematic Selection Framework

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Abstract

Background

Patients with rare diseases are fundamentally challenging to diagnose. Despite the fact that some estimates place rare diseases collectively as prevalent as one in ten, diagnosis can take >4 years and oftentimes much, much longer, and can lead to lifelong negative health consequences and early death. Expert diagnosticians and clinical geneticists are a scarce resource, and wait times for appointments are usually months to years. Therefore, there is an urgent need to assist healthcare systems and service providers of all kinds in improving diagnostic capabilities. AI and machine learning (AI/ML) make it far more feasible to help primary care and non-expert providers improve diagnosis for undiagnosed patients; however, there are no comprehensive, longitudinal, multimodal datasets available to train AI models that could be subsequently deployed in clinical settings.

Methodology

Our primary objective was to develop and apply a prioritization framework to identify rare diseases well-suited for diagnostic AI model development. The prioritization framework was designed as a foundational step to guide the selection of conditions for inclusion in the collection of multi-site, multi-modal benchmarking datasets. Our process was pragmatic: in recognition of limitations of evidence for multiple important factors, we incorporated expert consensus into the prioritization process. We prioritized diseases with low diagnostic rates relative to their prevalence and progressive and multi-system diseases where pleiotropic manifestations across specialties may be more amenable to signal detection. We considered the impact of diagnostic delay where earlier detection could meaningfully improve outcomes or where diagnosis would lead to actionable management changes. Finally, we considered the feasibility of confirming a suspected diagnosis and prioritized conditions with inexpensive or widely available tests.

Results

Our informatics approach leverages the Mondo disease classification, ontology-based characterization of phenotypic breadth and depth, real-world and published prevalence information, availability of therapeutics, and clinical expertise. We approximated which of the 16,403 rare disease classes in Mondo could be matched to similarly labeled ICD-10-CM or ICD-11 codes, finding a maximum similarity match of 2.7% and 15%, respectively. Using our prioritization framework, we selected 3,079 diseases (1,2) across all anatomical systems, including rare diseases with higher and lower prevalence. Preliminarily, approximately 9% of rare diseases had an approved or research grade drug associated.

Conclusions

Artificial intelligence advances are expected to greatly enhance diagnostic efficacy, but require quality data and benchmarking before they can be applied to clinical use. The outcome of the preliminary analysis presented here provides a robust, targetable set of rare diseases that would most likely benefit from the development of diagnostic AI models.

Background

The Rare Disease (RD) community faces significant challenges in timely diagnosis, health care delivery, and advancing research. According to the National Economic Burden of Rare Disease Study, more than 10,000 RDs affect 30M Americans, 50-75% of whom are children (3–5). With a total economic burden of nearly \$1 trillion (6), RDs present a major opportunity for innovation in diagnostic efficiency and therapeutic development. The diagnostic journey for RD patients remains arduous, characterized by non-specific initial symptoms, limited RD knowledge outside of tertiary care centers with disease specific expertise, delays in appropriate evaluation, referrals and testing, and additional barriers including lack of insurance coverage or access to specialists. Consequently it takes an average of >4-5 years to diagnose a RD (7); a large proportion of patients die without the correct diagnosis (8). Although currently less than 10% of RD have an FDA-approved treatment (9), 500-600 more are expected to be added to this list over the next decade (10,11); however, therapeutic windows are often time-bound and narrow, underscoring the importance of accurate and timely diagnoses.

Despite the healthcare burden imposed by RDs, the clinical and therapeutic advancements are limited by fragmentation of patient information across multiple clinical encounters with various specialities in different health care settings using various non-interoperable electronic health records, as well as research repositories, and other community resources. This fragmentation has been a barrier to better diagnose and understand the pathophysiology and response to treatment for these conditions. Furthermore, in clinical care settings many patient-specific clinical features are documented poorly if at all; this too is a challenge that AI can address. Clinical decision support for rare disease diagnostics and care is nearly absent at non-tertiary institutions, and as such, key phenotypic features required to aid diagnosis are not often collected. Tools such as the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO)(12) and PhenoTips (13), have aimed to narrow this gap, but are only used in highly specialized contexts outside the Electronic Health Record (EHR) and are limited in their ability to collect varied multi-modal phenotypic data more directly from patients, such as through voice, video, or structured self-report.

The application of AI/ML to assist recognition of patients with possible rare diseases, to help develop differential diagnoses in these cases, and to better understand disease progression will require “bootstrapping” with sufficient data to allow implementation and evaluation of AI tools. Even the less-complex task of identifying patients already diagnosed with RD within health records is non-trivial. The use of International Classification of Diseases (ICD) codes alone is inadequate because of a combination of inadequate granularity within branches of the coding space and inaccuracy or inconsistency of application of these codes within health records (14). ICD is a statistical classification used for morbidity/mortality reporting and administrative

purposes. ICD-10-CM is explicitly optimized for reporting and reimbursement, not for fine-grained clinical phenotyping or analytic uses. As a result, initial identification of RD patient cohorts for mechanistic and clinical insights, diagnostic screening, or study recruitment will need to be addressed not only through coding system improvements but by incorporating AI techniques such as large-language or large-multimodal models to recognize cohorts for whom aggregation can yield relevant health insights.

While many AI tools exist to aid genomic interpretation and/or EHR mining, these resources all suffer from the same problem - lack of access to high quality data for training. AI tools themselves do not generate data - they must be trained on high-quality, high-fidelity data to achieve good precision and recall. Such a RD dataset has never existed; commercial data is generated in the context of care, some RD registries capture detailed phenotypic information, but to date there has been no systematic effort to collate large scale clinical data sources including EHR, insurance claims, vision, dental, with registry data that includes patient provided content and multimodal data, often alongside multi-omics data. There is a good explanation for why such data are not available— there is little commercial benefit in any one organization tackling this challenge, and each individual RD community simply does not have the resources or expertise to do so. The ARPA-H solicitation under the Rare disease AI/ML and Precision Integrated Diagnostics (RAPID) program (15) is therefore a crucial opportunity to develop a public benefit resource that can foster not only improved healthcare for all, but also novel innovations in the commercial sector for diagnostics, clinical trial designs, and drug development.

In response to the RAPID solicitation to create a multimodal, high-quality, multi-institutional longitudinal collection of RD patient and control data for building AI diagnostic models and subsequent clinical decision support, we sought to prioritize which RDs would be most feasible targets and provide the best potential clinical outcomes if diagnostic AI models were developed. The RAPID program solicitation requested data collection within the first year involving over 500 rare diseases, subdivided by prevalence (along with 10x controls). Specifically, the solicitation specified that cohorts include at least 100 well documented "ultra-rare diseases" (prevalence <0.1/100k), at least 200 with intermediate prevalence (0.1-9/100k) and at least 200 with higher prevalence (10-50/100k). The overall goal is to establish techniques and demonstrate feasibility for collection of data for >85,000 patients (also with 10x controls) among >2700 rare diseases.

Here, we report the development and application of a prioritization framework as the initial step in this effort. Our analysis integrates disease ontologies, phenotypic characterization, prevalence estimation, treatment availability, and expert consensus to identify an initial set of target conditions. We highlight multiple factors in this framework for which there are evidence gaps or lack of broad data availability that pose a barrier to prioritization. As a specific example, we use an embedding-based comparison of rare disease terminology against ICD-10-CM and ICD-11 to illustrate one key barrier: the inadequacy of existing coding systems for identifying rare disease patients in real-world data.

Methods

Clinician members of the team collaboratively developed criteria for prioritization of diseases with respect to potential positive clinical and/or research impacts of inclusion in a large harmonized dataset (**Table 1**). This prioritization working group included members with expertise in medical genetics and genomics, pediatric and adult rare disease care, human genetics and phenotype-genotype curation, neurogenetics and developmental disorders, reproductive and developmental genetics, and hematology, and radiology. Evidence used in evaluating these criteria was collected in different ways for the different criteria described below.

Disease classification and terminology selection. We selected the Mondo Disease Ontology as the foundation for organization and representation of disease concepts due to its established ability to reconcile differences among exact and non-exact identifier matches among other resources in the RD community, coordinated by the Monarch Initiative, including Orphanet, OMIM, GARD, ClinGen, and many other sources (16,17).

Because our prioritization framework depends in part on estimating disease prevalence and identifying patient cohorts in EHRs, we first assessed how well current coding systems capture rare diseases. This assessment is a prerequisite for understanding which conditions can be feasibly identified through coded data and which will require alternative approaches.

Mondo has curated mappings to over 20 disease resources, together encompassing more than 87,000 unique mappings; however, the alignment of Mondo to ICD-10-CM and ICD-11 is still nascent. Thus, to approximate how well medical coding systems capture rare diseases, we instead used BioLORD-2023-C(18), an AI tool designed for biomedical language, to compare the names of over 16,403 known rare diseases in Mondo (both label and exact synonyms) against the codes available in two major classification systems: ICD-10-CM (the current U.S. standard) and ICD-11 Foundation. For each rare disease in Mondo, we looked for the closest matching code and quantified it by cosine similarity, scoring matches from 0 (no match) to 1 (perfect match).

Estimating disease prevalence. Prevalence data from the US population were provided through two means: search of relevant literature and targeted evaluations of numbers of patients in planned recruitment sites using EHR data. These data had been deidentified using the Expert Determination methodology, thus categorizing this preliminary data collection as Non-Human Subjects Research.

Classification of diseases with low diagnostic rate compared to expected prevalence or where diagnostic delay may affect optimal treatment. The probability of escaping detection through current standards of care was difficult to assess in an automated fashion because of lack of consistent data on both expected prevalence and diagnostic rates, so we relied on manual literature review and expert experience of delayed diagnosis as a proxy for diseases that may be underrecognized. We likewise prioritized conditions in which guidelines support the importance of early management.

Presence of registry data and/or targetable populations for recruitment. We combined multiple approaches to assess the presence of specialty clinics or registries within our partner network and beyond. We evaluated locus-specific databases, publicly available disease registries (including Global Genes, NORD, RDCRN, CZI, and MATRIX platforms), and through partner engagement quantified the number of individuals enrolled in shareable registries. Where possible, we performed de-identified queries of EHR data (e.g., Slicer-Dicer searches using ICD-10-CM or SNOMED CT codes for unique patients seen within the past five years). As candidate cohorts were identified, we expanded queries across partner sites to build a comprehensive view. For conditions not readily captured due to coding limitations, we estimated recruitment potential using the total patient populations of contributing health systems and published prevalence data (e.g., Orphanet (19)), applying a conservative adjustment factor (0.2) such that estimated enrollment = $0.2 \times \text{total patient population} \times \text{disease prevalence}$.

Treatment availability. Availability of treatment information was gathered from MeDIC, a foundational resource covering diseases, drugs, indications and contraindications (20) and provenance linked to Mondo rare diseases (1). We enhanced MeDIC with additional provenance content for the purposes of this analysis.

Presence of phenotypic variation. To address the potential for identification by disease characteristics (e.g., progressive, multisystem diseases), we created a metric that calculates breadth and depth of the HPO annotations based on information content. This measures the

specificity of terms as well as characterizing the breadth of anatomical systems affected. We used disease phenotype profiles for ~8000 RDs. HPO profiles, when available, are shown in “Justification Grouping: curated HPO profiles” in Supplementary Table 1. Stepwise methods are as follows:

- Information content (IC) scores for HPO terms were calculated using the oaklib semantic framework (21) with disease-phenotype associations from the HPO Annotations (HPOA) resource as the background corpus (12). IC is defined as the negative \log_2 of the probability of observing a term or any of its descendants in the annotation corpus (22). Rarely-used (more specific) phenotype terms have higher IC values.
- Each phenotype annotation was mapped to one or more of 20 high-level anatomical and physiological systems defined by HPO organ system branches based upon underlying Uberon (23) anatomical classes: skeletal (HP:0000924), nervous (HP:0000707), head and neck (HP:0000152), integument (HP:0001574), eye (HP:0000478), cardiovascular (HP:0001626), metabolism/homeostasis (HP:0001939), genitourinary (HP:0000119), digestive (HP:0025031), neoplasm (HP:0002664), blood (HP:0001871), immune (HP:0002715), endocrine (HP:0000818), musculature (HP:0003011), respiratory (HP:0002086), ear (HP:0000598), connective tissue (HP:0003549), prenatal/birth (HP:0001197), growth (HP:0001507), and breast (HP:0000769).
- Assignment was determined using the ontology closure, i.e. the set of all ancestor terms reachable by following subclass (rdfs:subClassOf) and part-of (BFO:0000050) relationships in the HPO hierarchy. A phenotype term was assigned to a system if that system's root term appeared in its closure. For example, "Aortic valve stenosis" (HP:0001650) has "Abnormality of the cardiovascular system" (HP:0001626) in its closure via the path: Aortic valve stenosis → Abnormal aortic valve morphology → Abnormal heart valve morphology → Abnormal heart morphology → Abnormality of the cardiovascular system. Thus, a disease annotated with "Aortic valve stenosis" would receive credit for cardiovascular system involvement. A single phenotype term may map to multiple systems when its closure includes multiple system root terms.
- For each Mondo disease and system pair, we computed the mean IC of all phenotype annotations for that disease within that system. The final breadth score was calculated as the sum of these mean IC values across all affected systems. This formulation ensures that diseases affecting more organ systems receive higher scores, while also weighting systems with more specific (higher IC) phenotype annotations more heavily.
- We combined the breadth/depth metric with the presence of a known treatment to rank RDs (column “HPO profile and treatment - based rank”).

Combining prioritization criteria for phase I data collection. In recognition that many conditions do not have available evidence needed to quantitatively evaluate one or more of these criteria, the proposed inclusion of specific diseases in our phase I data collection was guided by consensus among the clinical and health informatics experts in our team.

Table 1. Disease prioritization criteria rationale and examples

Prioritization criterion	Criterion rationale	Example conditions	Condition rationale
Existence of a registry or specialty clinic within the network	Existing longitudinal registry or health system cohorts with expertise to validate phenotypes and AI models.	Angelman syndrome	Angelman Syndrome Foundation (24) UNC Angelman Syndrome Clinic (25)
		Mucopolysaccharidoses	Registry and UNC specialty center (26)
		Fanconi Anemia	Registry (27) and UNC researchers (28)
		Congenital hyperinsulinism	Registry (29)
Low diagnostic rates for higher prevalence RDs	Higher number of undiagnosed patients, bigger impact in patient numbers, potential for improved recognition through computational phenotyping	Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency	Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency remains significantly underdiagnosed, with fewer than 10% of the estimated 100,000 affected Americans identified despite its prevalence in approximately 1% to 5% of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (30,31).
		22q11 deletion	22q11.2 deletion syndrome is the most common chromosomal microdeletion, yet it remains significantly underdiagnosed due to its highly variable clinical presentation and the absence of typical physical features in many affected individuals. Approximately 10% of 22q11.2 deletions are inherited from a parent, but that parent may not have been previously diagnosed because of the subtlety of clinical presentation in some individuals (32,33).
		Ehlers-Danlos Syndrome	Ehlers-Danlos syndromes, particularly the hypermobile subtype, frequently remain underdiagnosed or misdiagnosed for years due to nonspecificity of early clinical findings, a lack of clinical awareness, and the absence of definitive genetic testing— despite current research indicating a significantly higher prevalence than previously estimated (34,35).
		Hereditary Hemorrhagic Telangiectasia	Hereditary hemorrhagic telangiectasia is significantly underdiagnosed due to its variable clinical expressivity and age-related variability in clinical phenotype, with recent genetic analyses suggesting a true prevalence two to twelve times higher than current clinical estimates (36,37).
		Fabry Disease	Fabry disease remains significantly underdiagnosed due to its heterogeneous, multisystemic presentation and the high prevalence of late-onset phenotypes that often mimic more common conditions, resulting in diagnostic delays that average over a decade (38,39).
Progressive/ multi-system diseases	Potential for recognition of pleiotropic features across medical specialties, multiple manifestations for potential treatments	Pompe disease	Pompe disease is a progressive lysosomal storage disorder characterized by the systemic accumulation of glycogen due to acid alpha-glucosidase deficiency, leading to debilitating multisystemic involvement that primarily affects cardiac, respiratory, and skeletal muscle functions (40,41).
		Fabry disease	Fabry disease is a progressive, multisystemic lysosomal storage disorder where the accumulation of globotriaosylceramide leads to worsening dysfunction across the renal, cardiac, cerebrovascular, and peripheral nervous systems (42,43).
		Amyloidosis	Amyloidosis is a heterogeneous group of protein misfolding disorders characterized by the extracellular deposition of insoluble fibrils across multiple organ systems, including the heart, kidneys, and liver, leading to progressive organ dysfunction and eventual failure (44,45).

Prioritization criterion	Criterion rationale	Example conditions	Condition rationale
		Neuronal Ceroid Lipofuscinoses (NCLs)	Neuronal ceroid lipofuscinoses are progressive neurodegenerative lysosomal storage disorders characterized by a debilitating triad of symptoms, including refractory epilepsy, vision loss, and cognitive and motor decline, leading to multi-system involvement and premature death (46,47).
		Myotonic dystrophy	Myotonic dystrophy is a progressive, multisystemic genetic disorder characterized by evolving muscle atrophy and myotonia alongside significant complications across the cardiovascular, respiratory, gastrointestinal, endocrine, and central nervous systems (48,49).
Diagnostic delay impact	Patients face prolonged diagnostic odysseys, and earlier detection via aggregated real-world data can improve outcomes.	PTEN hamartoma tumor syndrome	Delayed diagnosis of PTEN hamartoma tumor syndrome prevents the implementation of established clinical guidelines for intensive cancer surveillance, significantly increasing the risk of advanced-stage malignancies due to the high cumulative lifetime risk of breast, thyroid, renal, and endometrial cancers (50).
		Paroxysmal nocturnal haemoglobinuria	Diagnostic delay in paroxysmal nocturnal haemoglobinuria significantly increases the risk of life-threatening complications, such as hemolysis, thromboembolic events and chronic kidney disease, whereas timely diagnosis and initiation of complement inhibitor therapy can prevent organ damage and improve health-related quality of life (51).
		Fibrodysplasia ossificans progressiva	Early diagnosis of fibrodysplasia ossificans progressiva is critical to prevent iatrogenic harm from unnecessary invasive procedures, such as biopsies or surgeries, which trigger irreversible heterotopic ossification and accelerate permanent loss of mobility (52,53).
Indicated management change	Prioritizes RDs that are actionable (i.e. prescribe treatment, assess cancer risk, refer to specialist, refer to trial)	Li Fraumeni syndrome	Li Fraumeni syndrome confers substantial cancer risk, and there are guidelines for lifelong surveillance protocols—such as annual whole-body and brain MRIs starting at birth. In the context of Li Fraumeni syndrome, cancer treatment may also be modified to minimize radiation exposure, which is known to induce secondary malignancies in these patients (54,55).
		Gaucher disease	Prompt diagnosis of Gaucher disease is critical because delayed intervention allows for the accumulation of glucocerebroside, leading to irreversible complications such as avascular necrosis, permanent organ damage, and skeletal deformities. Many complications can be prevented or stabilized through established clinical guidelines and FDA-approved therapies, including enzyme replacement therapies and oral substrate reduction therapies (56,57).
		Transthyretin amyloidosis	Early diagnosis of transthyretin amyloidosis is critical because disease-modifying therapies, including FDA-approved TTR stabilizers like tafamidis and acoramidis and gene silencers like vutrisiran, are most effective when initiated before significant organ damage or symptomatic progression occurs (58,59).
Inexpensive, less invasive, or widely available test	Availability of confirmation after computational identification; improve utilization of medically appropriate test	Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency	Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency can be definitively and non-invasively diagnosed through widely available, inexpensive blood tests that quantify serum protein levels and identify genetic variants or phenotypes (60).
		Wilson disease	Wilson disease can be diagnosed through relatively simple and non-invasive methods, primarily utilizing serum ceruloplasmin levels and 24-hour urinary copper excretion measurements, which are widely available and cost-effective screening tools (61).
		Rare monogenic dyslipidemias	Rare monogenic dyslipidemias meet this criterion because they can be definitively diagnosed using targeted next-generation sequencing panels, which offer a non-invasive, cost-effective, and highly accurate alternative to traditional Sanger sequencing (62).

Prioritization criterion	Criterion rationale	Example conditions	Condition rationale
		Hypophosphatasia	Hypophosphatasia can be accurately identified through a widely available and inexpensive blood test measuring persistently low, age-adjusted alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity (63).
		Fanconi Anemia	Fanconi anemia can be reliably confirmed by genetic sequencing. Even if pathogenic variants cannot be identified, the diepoxybutane (DEB) chromosomal breakage test, a widely available and inexpensive peripheral blood assay that exploits the hallmark hypersensitivity of FA cells to DNA cross-linking agents, provides definitive functional results from a standard blood draw without the need for invasive procedures (64,65).
		Diamond-Blackfan anemia	Diamond-Blackfan anemia can be identified through routine blood work revealing macrocytic anemia with reticulocytopenia, and further confirmed by measuring erythrocyte adenosine deaminase (eADA) activity - a widely available, inexpensive blood test with 84% sensitivity and 95% specificity that outperforms genetic sequencing in detection rate (66).

Phenotypic complexity and / or multimodal detectability	Phenotype signatures exist with established genomic, imaging, and/or lab-based features; AI models that work in the context of general care are realizable	X-linked hypophosphatemia (XLH)	X-linked hypophosphatemia exhibits significant phenotypic complexity through a multimodal signature of chronic phosphate wasting, including diagnostic biochemical markers (low serum phosphorus and elevated FGF23), characteristic radiographic evidence of rickets and enthesopathy, and confirmatory PHEX gene mutational analysis (67,68).
		Turner Syndrome	Turner Syndrome exhibits high phenotypic complexity and multimodal detectability through distinctive clinical signatures, such as short stature and webbed neck, that are corroborated by established genomic karyotyping, prenatal ultrasound imaging, and biochemical markers like elevated follicle-stimulating hormone (69,70) and that may distinguish from other conditions (like Noonan Syndrome) which can have overlapping clinical features.
		Telomere disorders	Telomere biology disorders present a complex phenotypic spectrum ranging from a classic mucocutaneous triad to multi-organ failure, supported by well-defined diagnostic signatures including leukocyte telomere length testing via flow-FISH and comprehensive germline genetic panels (71,72).
		Glycogen storage diseases	Glycogen storage disease Ia exhibits phenotypic complexity through distinct metabolic disruptions, enabling the development of machine learning models that accurately identify patients by integrating established biochemical biomarkers (73).

Results

Definition of key criteria for prioritization To maximize the potential impact of the prospective dataset, members of the proposal team collaboratively identified multiple factors to prioritize 3,079 conditions, along with conditions that exemplify these criteria (**Table 1**).

- The first criterion for inclusion was the presence of an existing registry or speciality clinic within our respective hospitals. Confirmed, registry-enrolled patients serve as critical phenotypic anchors, enabling computable phenotype development and validation that cannot be achieved from coded EHR data alone, especially where rare disease coding coverage remains critically incomplete. The presence of existing registries or specialty clinics within the collaborative was also considered as enhancing feasibility of raw data collection through existing resources, and as providing likelihood of productive engagement with active research and patient communities.
- The second criterion was to identify conditions where low diagnostic rates were present for RDs experts determined to be relatively high prevalence, which would have significant health impact through improved recognition.
- The third criterion focused on the potential for recognition of pleiotropic features across different organ systems. The rationale for this criterion was three-fold. Having a breadth and depth of potential phenotypic characteristics may indicate a greater likelihood of recognizing a diagnostic signal in real world care data. This is in contrast to the numerous RDs that have a few, common manifestations; for example ‘intellectual disability’ in a pediatric setting may warrant running a genomic test - no diagnostic AI model is needed for nonsyndromic conditions. Second, multi-system diseases are often missed in primary care or individual speciality care that may focus on clinical features in limited body systems; the outcomes of AI/ML models could provide Clinical Decision Support (CDS) in such contexts. Further, the presence of multiple manifestations could be targetable by different potential treatments, thereby alleviating some of the negative health outcomes, especially progressive ones, even if only for a subset of signs and symptoms.

Several of the most important criteria were regarding the negative consequences of not having a correct diagnosis and the change in care management given a correct diagnosis. We prioritized conditions with direct clinical actionability considering those listed in the ACMG secondary findings reporting guidance (74), designated as having strong or definitive actionability by the ClinGen Actionability working group (75), as well as those with available treatments. In some cases, clinical trials were also manually identified in ClinicalTrials.gov; we plan to expand this systematic evaluation. While acknowledging the personal utility of being able to provide a specific diagnosis and complete the diagnostic odyssey, our consideration of actionability prioritizes conditions where direct changes in medical management, e.g., through clinical decision support, could be made if patient identification could be improved. We also prioritized conditions for which readily available diagnostic tests were available, for example hypophosphatasia where history of fractures and persistently low alkaline phosphatase could point towards diagnosis.

Finally, given that a significant expected downstream use of a combined dataset would be as training data for AI models, we also considered the potential for conditions to manifest identifiable signatures across multimodal data amenable to clinical applications and prospective model development.

Identification of evidence gaps hindering systematic prioritization As summarized in **Table 2**, we encountered difficulty in systematic prioritization using existing structured data sources. Many of these had been anticipated based on prior literature regarding sparsity of data across

individual rare diseases, so as a pragmatic initial approach, we relied on expert experience and consensus in our initial prioritization, while also categorizing these limitations and gathering preliminary evidence to characterize the potential impact of evidence gaps.

Table 2: Evidence gaps encountered during disease prioritization

Evidence gap	Description	Proposed mitigation for iterative future work
Diagnostic code coverage	Most rare diseases lack a specific code in ICD-10-CM or ICD-11, limiting the ability to identify patient cohorts from coded data.	Combine multiple coding systems (ICD-10-CM, ICD-11, SNOMED CT) with mapping between e.g., LOINC to HPO and embedding-based mapping to develop computable phenotypes anchored to registry-verified cases rather than codes alone. Improve Mondo RD inclusion in EHRs and within ICD and SNOMED
Prevalence estimates	United States prevalence data were unavailable for most conditions. Only 140 diseases could be confidently classified as “higher prevalence.”	Derive site-specific deidentified prevalence estimates from linked real-world data across partner health systems and registries to enable reports of uncertainty rather than single point estimates.
Diagnostic rate and delay	Related to gaps in prevalence data, the rate of “potential undiagnosed individuals” or time from initial symptoms to diagnosis could not be quantified for most conditions, requiring reliance on expert experience as a proxy.	Estimate pre-diagnostic intervals from registry-linked longitudinal records and from historical data for patients identified through computational phenotypes.
Treatment and actionability data	MeDIC and similar resources provide structured information about approved or research-grade drugs, but do not capture information about which drugs clinicians might reasonably consider using off-label, nor information about personal utility.	Augment structured drug-indication resources with guideline-based actionability (e.g., ACMG secondary findings and ClinGen Actionability), incorporate patent-reported measures of personal utility from registry data. Develop process for continuous inclusion of drugs under investigation.
Phenotypic characterization	HPO Annotation phenotype profiles are only available for about half of the Mondo ontology rare disease classes, so many conditions lack curated phenotype annotations required to compute the breadth/depth metric. Furthermore, many HPOA profiles are based on small cohorts in the medical literature, and subject to ascertainment bias.	Expand phenotype coverage from iterative development of profiles among the target dataset. Improve phenotypic characterization using EHR data and additional terminologies.

The mapping of the Mondo disease concepts to ICD-10-CM and ICD-11 illustrates how gaps in clinical code coverage lead to difficulty in identifying patient cohorts. ICD-11 was an improvement over ICD-10-CM, both in terms of number of concepts mapping and in similarity of the matches, with average match scores rising from about 0.6 to 0.75–0.80. But as shown in **Figure 1**, the overall picture is still bleak: the vast majority of rare diseases present in Mondo still don't have an equivalent in medical coding systems.

Figure 1. Number of Mondo diseases that had a closely matching code (at 0.9 cosine similarity or above) in ICD-10-CM or ICD-11.

Illustrating this lack-of-coding problem with a specific group of disorders (disorders of phosphorus metabolism, under the E83.3 cluster in ICD-10-CM) demonstrates the challenges for declustering and for estimation of prospective cohort sizes (and by extension, prevalence). Among three academic medical centers in the proposed team, the vast majority of cases are categorized in “Other disorders of phosphorus metabolism” (E83.39). While distinct from standalone hyperphosphatemia (which would be coded as E87.5), this code would include conditions caused by malnutrition, malabsorption (for instance, secondary to Crohn’s disease), primary genetic metabolic disorders, and kidney diseases.

Table 3. Counts of individuals with disorder of phosphorus metabolism and phosphatases across selected sites in our project team.

Concept Code and Description	Truveta	UNCHealth	Johns Hopkins	Emory
Disorders of phosphorus metabolism and phosphatases (ICD10CM:E83.3)	846,487	23,180	29,858	26,313
Disorder of phosphorus metabolism, unspecified (ICD10CM:E83.30)	27,594	630	156	1,366
Familial hypophosphatemia (ICD10CM:E83.31)	2,703	1,500	221	726
Hereditary vitamin D-dependent rickets (type 1) (type 2) (ICD10CM:E83.32)	1,434	190	41	32
Other disorders of phosphorus metabolism (ICD10CM:E83.39)	824,498	22,640	29,440	25,582

Individuals were identified by ICD-10-CM codes alone from deidentified datasets. Counts for the E83.3 category are aggregated from within the subcategories. Diagnostic codes among UNCHealth (UNC), Johns Hopkins University (JHU) and Emory are for unique patients by site with those diagnoses codes from May 2021-May 2026.

Application of initial prioritization process. We prioritized 3,079 diseases as targets for building AI-based diagnostic models that would eventually lead to improved clinical decision support and prospective data acquisition regarding patients with these candidate diseases (Supplemental Table 1). These disorders collectively have clinical features across a wide breadth of anatomical systems, including many conditions that affect multiple systems (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Distribution of prioritized rare diseases by anatomical system. The high level Mondo hierarchy under MONDO:7770006 (disease by body system or component) provides an organizational structure to evaluate the breadth of body systems represented among the prioritized conditions. Percentages are given among the 3,079 prioritized conditions, and across the categories sum to more than 100% because the Mondo classification allows for diseases to be present in more than one category.

We used prevalence categories as defined in the RAPID solicitation which defined higher prevalence as ~10-50/100k and lower prevalence as ~0.1-9/100k. Out of the 3,079 RDs curated by our team, we were only able to identify 140 that we could confidently say met ARPA-H’s “higher” prevalence definition (Figure 3). Our initial set of diseases contain more “lower” prevalence diseases for a total of 2,926.

Figure 3. Prevalence of prioritized diseases. Low prevalence threshold (for solicitation purposes) was ~0.1-9/100k, and high prevalence ~10-50/100k.

Discussion

The challenges demonstrated in the prioritization process illustrate precisely the challenges that prompted the RAPID program solicitation. There is scarcity of diagnostic code coverage for many rare conditions, requiring use of multiple coding systems and alternative strategies in an attempt to develop rubrics for case identification. Phenotypic complexity among these conditions, and the resulting variability of description by clinicians of different specialities (who for a specific patient may even be at different institutions) is expected to further confound definitive recognition of patients. Moreover ultra-rare diseases present even greater challenges for initial model development; however, the infrastructure and methodologies we will establish are specifically designed to be extensible to all rare diseases. By validating our approaches with conditions where feasibility can be demonstrated, we aim to create a foundation that will ultimately enable better diagnostic tools for even the rarest conditions, where the need is often greatest.

There are still substantial challenges in characterizing the prevalence of rare diseases.

First, there is no agreement in what constitutes designating a disease rare (i.e. in the US, a rare disease affects fewer than 200,000 people; in the European Union, fewer than 5 per 10,000), and regional prevalence varies (e.g. sickle cell anemia). For disease with no codes, we estimated prevalence based upon literature reporting (“Potential data sources” column). We know the accuracy of these estimates is limited by several factors, including RD enrichment due to the presence of specialty clinics and/or underreporting. There is no established threshold for high and low incidence in RD, the RAPID solicitation’s division at 10/100k is notable because papers published in subspecialty medical genetics journals (76) posit ~1/100k as the dividing line between conditions considered “common” and “rare”. Recent global efforts aim to reconcile definition of rare designation (77) - though such efforts will suffer from the same challenges in assessing prevalence described herein.

Despite targeted attempts by multiple data science and clinical genetics experts to identify higher prevalence rare diseases, we were only able to confidently identify 140, suggesting this represents the actual epidemiological distribution rather than an incomplete search. It is worth noting that prevalence may be underestimated based on ascertainment of clinically symptomatic individuals; in conditions characterized by incomplete penetrance and variable expressivity, we may find that the population prevalence of individuals with disease-associated genotypes is higher than expected.

The need for consistent definitions of disease entities.

Medical conditions can be defined observationally or mechanistically. In the former, a disease entity might be defined through clinical criteria such as collection of observed manifestations over time, while the latter, especially for genetic diseases, focuses on the underlying factor(s) causing disease. The question of whether to group or separate related conditions is important for cohort definition and guides subsequent inference that can be made from collected data. The ClinGen consortium has developed a standardized process for determining whether “lumping or splitting” of disease entities (based on molecular mechanism, phenotypic specificity, and inheritance pattern) should take place for the purposes of consideration of validity of assertions of gene-disease relationships (78). This need justified our use of Mondo, which not only partners with ClinGen to capture lumping and splitting guidance and nomenclature, but also

because it reconciles conflicting definitions across many global resources in a collaborative fashion. We also note the challenge in selecting RDs for prioritization in the context of lumping vs. splitting of distinct subsets of diseases (e.g., with Gaucher disease by different onset/severity; or grouping together Nevroid Basal Cell Carcinoma Syndrome cases vs. separating them into individual monogenic disease entities caused by either pathogenic variants in *PTCH1* or *SUFU*).

Target counts for “higher prevalence” rare diseases could not be met.

Penetrance/severity and prevalence are typically inversely related. By linking registry cohorts to their longitudinal real-world clinical records, it becomes possible to learn what each disease looked like in ordinary care settings prior to diagnosis: which laboratory values were abnormal, which specialist referrals were made, which symptoms appeared in clinical notes years before a formal diagnosis was recorded. This pre-diagnostic signal, learned from verified patients, can then be applied across large populations to identify currently undiagnosed individuals, a capability that depends entirely on the combination of registry depth and real-world data breadth that this program uniquely assembles. Identifying patients through this signal may help better approach the target goals for higher prevalence rare diseases, or conversely could help provide additional support that the low count of diseases in this category reflects actual epidemiology.

Limitations and future directions

This work represents an initial and deliberately pragmatic step. We acknowledge that its scope is constrained by the evidence and resources available at this stage of rare disease research, but in recognition that production of an ambitious dataset as described in the RAPID solicitation will require subsequent iteration. The prioritization was guided by expert consensus when quantitative evidence was sparse (**Table 2**), and as a consequence the selection should be understood as a defensible starting set rather than one that has been exhaustively validated. We have not yet performed inferential testing or formal optimization of the prioritization criteria. We report the framework and its inputs transparently, intending for its selection to be revisited and refined as additional data become available.

Several future priorities follow directly from the gaps summarized in **Table 2**. First, the framework generates testable predictions that can be evaluated prospectively when multimodal data collection is underway: namely that prioritized diseases will exhibit greater multimodal detectability and higher recruitment feasibility than non-prioritized conditions. By establishing measurable success criteria for each of these domains, we will be able to quantify the added value of the framework. Second, expansion of expert contribution in future iterations will allow a formal assessment of the consensus process for aspects of the framework that still face significant evidence gaps. Because much of the prioritization relied on expert experience, future iterations should have a representative subset of conditions scored by independent reviewers blinded to local clinic or registry presence, with inter-rater agreement reported (e.g., Cohen's kappa or intraclass correlation) and disagreements adjudicated through a documented procedure. Third, the phenotypic and coding analyses each rest on resources with known limitations. The breadth/depth metric is computable only for the roughly half of Mondo rare disease classes with curated HPO annotations (curated from OMIM, Orphanet, and Decipher), and those annotations are themselves drawn largely from small published cohorts subject to ascertainment bias; external validation of this metric against clinician-rated complexity and against downstream model performance in exemplar conditions is an important next step, and may itself further demonstrate the field's need for a richer catalog of phenotypic expression and variability. Finally, realizing this work at scale carries governance and equity obligations. The preliminary data described here were limited to aggregate, de-identified queries, and the registry linkage the program envisions is planned rather than performed; its implementation will require explicit attention to consent and patient and community oversight. Given the systematic

underrepresentation of underserved populations noted below, prospective evaluation of model fairness across ancestry, geography, age, and access to specialty care will be a necessary component of future validation.

Why registries, coding, and linked data are synergistic in building AI diagnostic models.

The infrastructure and methodology that RAPID aims to achieve are specifically designed to address gaps that alternative data approaches cannot solve. For example, datasets derived from genomic testing only after diagnostic suspicion has already been raised reflect populations that have already entered specialty care and therefore do not reveal the pre-diagnostic period where earlier intervention would have the greatest impact. EHR data is constrained by existing coding systems, which have very poor coverage of rare diseases. For example, the vast majority of RDs are missing from ICD-10-CM/ICD-11 (**Figure 1**) indicating that rare diseases remain systematically under-represented in both coding systems and suggest that embedding-based gap analysis can identify specific diseases lacking adequate ICD representation. Enhancements to EHRs so as to include Mondo rare disease concepts are underway but will take significant effort and time to realize in downstream analytics. Further, access to EHR and claims data for RD patients is extremely sparse and access terms are aligned with commercial rather than public health objectives. The approach we propose is to link verified registry cohorts to large-scale real-world data through privacy-preserving, standards-based infrastructure governed as a public resource (79) to ensure that the data are vendor-agnostic, continuously extensible, and designed to support open benchmarking and model comparison across diseases and clinical settings. This distinction matters not only for data completeness but for equity: rare disease patients in rural settings, underserved communities, or without access to specialty centers are systematically underrepresented in datasets derived from those who have already received advanced diagnostic workup. Reaching these patients requires population-level identification starting from undiagnosed individuals in routine care, which is only achievable when registry-verified phenotypes are applied across broad, multimodal, multi-institutional real-world data at the scale this program proposes.

Conclusions

This study successfully initiated a targetable set of 3,079 rare diseases most likely to benefit from the development of diagnostic AI models. The prioritization framework focused on conditions with low diagnostic rates relative to their prevalence, progressive and multi-system features, a high impact from diagnostic delay, and those where diagnosis would lead to actionable management changes or confirmation via inexpensive and widely available tests. Gaps in medical coding systems, existing underdiagnosis, and lack of documentation of the patient's biological features in EHRs are what make it difficult not only to build diagnostic AI models, but even to select them for this purpose. These challenges point to the great necessity to obtain longitudinal, multimodal registry data from rare disease cohorts together with real-world data obtained through privacy-preserving and standards-based approaches. Such comprehensive, longitudinal data are critical for capturing the pre-diagnostic signal needed to identify currently undiagnosed individuals in routine care, thereby reducing the diagnostic odyssey as well as promoting equitable diagnostic access for patients. We also recognize that the advancements in AI-based diagnostics will continue to evolve and inform the development of clinical decision support to improve diagnostic efficiency and efficacy in primary care and resource or expertise-limited contexts. Our initial work establishes a foundation that will continue to refine targets for AI diagnostic model building and inform the development of clinical decision support to improve diagnostic efficiency and efficacy in all contexts for all diseases.

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